

6G-DALI: an End-to-End AI Framework for Automating Data and ML Operations

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Abstract—Native support of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) is one of the pillars of future 6G networks. Despite the opportunities, there are several gaps that are hindering the seamless adoption of AI/ML in 6G. The lack of rich and high-quality datasets needed to train and fine-tune the models, and the need to test and evaluate AI models in a representative staging environment while ensuring ethics and regulatory compliance, represents a challenge without access to an end-to-end 6G testbed or a representative Digital Twin (DT) replica environment. To this end, 6G-DALI, the new SNS-JU Phase-3 project on Reliable AI for 6G Communications Systems and Services, aims at providing an end-to-end AI framework for 6G, structured around two interdependent pillars: AI experimentation as a service via Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) and Data and analytics collection and storage via Data Operations (DataOps). Finally, 6G-DALI will deliver a 6G Dataspace for dataset storage and secure sharing, and a Digital Twin (DT) testbed for data generation on demand.

Keywords — MLOps, DataOps, Data Spaces, Digital Twins, Trustworthy AI, Generative AI.

I. AI/ML AS 6G KEY ENABLER

One of the key enablers of 6G networks is the native support of AI/ML at all system levels, from orchestration and management to the low-level optimization of the network resources at different domains (radio access, transport, core) [1]. The integration of AI/ML in 6G will not only impact key stakeholders such as network operators and telco manufacturers, but also verticals which are increasingly relying on AI/ML to optimize their applications and services running on top of the mobile networks, as well as standards development operators and policy makers to ensure AI/ML complies with the harmonized standards [2] and rules of laws.

A. Related work

As AI/ML is emerging as a key enabler for 6G, several standardization bodies are tackling AI/ML as part of their standardization activities: ETSI, CEN/CLC, 3GPP, O-RAN, and TM Forum are all leveraging AI/ML as a key enabler for managing complex network infrastructures in support of heterogeneous 6G use cases to enable advanced functionalities for AI-driven zero-touch network and service management

[2], Network Data Analytics Functions (NWDAF) [3], radio resource optimization [4], and intent driven automation [5]. In addition, several ongoing European funded research and innovation projects are focusing their efforts in defining the role of AI/ML in 6G networks and are working to identify gaps, ethics and regulatory challenges and technology enablers for its adoption. The 6G flagship HEXAX-II [6] project, as well as SNS-JU Phase 1 and 2 projects (which focus on evolutionary 6G technology and systems), such as ADROIT-6G [7] and 6G-INTENSE [8], are proposing novel 6G architectures that integrate AI/ML through advanced MLOps and crowdsourcing platforms for distributed and collaborative AI. On the other hand, experimentation and vertical trials oriented projects such as 6G-BRICKS [9] and SUNRISE-6G [10] already started to define a standard approach for experimenters to deploy, test and validate Trustworthy AI/ML models.

B. Remaining gaps for AI/ML adoption 6G

The increasing computing power available, the scaling laws of ML together with theoretical advances, have driven progress in many areas of AI/ML, such as distributed and federated learning (DFL/FL), reinforcement learning (RL), and more recently with the breakthrough of generative AI (GenAI) and large language models (LLM) [11]. However, two major remaining gaps limit the adoption of AI/ML in 6G. First, the need of extensive datasets to train models and the quality of data have a critical impact on the accuracy of the resulting model. For this purpose, the International Data Space (IDS) [12] and Gaia-X [13] initiatives aim at providing a secure and sovereign framework to generate data to build ML models. While these initiatives focus on the generation of Data Spaces for critical sectors such as health, agriculture, and manufacturing, data spaces efforts for 6G datasets are indeed very limited. Second, when an AI/ML model is developed, testing and validating its performance in a representative environment remains a challenge. While model validation platforms may help to validate a model, they have a strong limitation when it comes to representing real and complex environments like 6G systems. To this end, MLOps systems provide a set of reproducible workflows for the development, test and validation of AI/ML models in staging environments for performance benchmarking prior to

deployment in production. In the context of 6G, this should evolve towards relevant 6G staging environments (e.g., 6G testbeds and 6G Network DTs).

II. 6G-DALI END-TO-END AI FRAMEWORK

6G-DALI, the new SNS-JU Phase-3 project on Reliable AI for 6G Communications Systems and Services, aims at filling the gaps identified in section I.B by building a novel end-to-end AI framework that aims to connect 6G data with vertical industries, ML developers and experimenters, while relying on 6G testbeds selected from the SUNRISE-6G project. To this end, 6G-DALI is bringing together three communities: experts in the design and experimentation on 6G technology enablers, experts on AI and MLOps systems, and finally experts on DataOps and Data Spaces to build an efficient, realistic, and trustworthy framework for end-to-end AI/ML experimentation in support of advanced 6G use cases and services. To fulfill this vision, the end-to-end 6G-DALI AI framework is structured, as per Fig. 1, upon two interdependent pillars: MLOps and DataOps, which are further detailed in the subsequent sections. To this end, and to facilitate the integration of additional testbeds and DT environments, 6G-DALI adopts a flexible and modular plugin-based approach. This allows to introduce dedicated connectors towards the underlying testbed specific APIs and resources to enforce AI/ML model test scenarios, network traffic models, data patterns to generate, while offering to the core AI framework unified interfaces and data models.

Fig. 1: 6G-DALI high level architecture

A. AI/ML Experimentation as a service via MLOps

The adoption of MLOps techniques facilitate the development, continuous training, testing, validation, hyperparameter optimization, and continuous monitoring of AI/ML models throughout their lifecycle, with effective workflow management. In the 6G-DALI vision, existing MLOps solutions and systems (e.g. from ADROIT-6G and 6G-INTENSE projects) are enhanced to fully support Reinforcement Learning Operations (RLOps) and Automated Hyperparameters Optimization (HPO) to fine-tune models for optimal use of testbed resources in the far-edge/edge/cloud continuum, as well as to integrate Transfer Learning mechanisms. Moreover, 6G-DALI aims at augmenting the MLOps capabilities of the proposed AI framework introducing a meta-orchestrator for overarching and coordinating the heterogeneous MLOps tools and APIs possibly adopted in the various 6G testbeds. By enhancing existing MLOps systems and federating them across the available 6G testbeds, the 6G-DALI meta-orchestration solution

will provide an automated, scalable, and collaborative end-to-end AI experimentation framework that ensures efficiency trustworthiness and adaptability for 6G AI/ML deployments and service.

B. Data collection, storage and sharing via DataOps

Existing DataOps solutions, such as those used in GAIA-X and IDS, are the state-of-the-art solutions for generating, validating and sharing valuable datasets for data analytics and AI/ML model training. 6G-DALI aims at integrating these solutions as key technology enablers, and adapt them to address the complexity of 6G networks and use cases. For this, 6G-DALI will deliver advanced DataOps functionalities to create a 6G Data Space that connects different 6G testbeds and enable 6G data sharing, ensuring that datasets are easily discoverable, cataloged and available for models training and validation. In addition, the 6G DALI DataOps will adopt the concept of ELT (Extract, Load, Transform) pipelines to clean, structure and categorize data. Moreover, GenAI will allow to simplify these processes by enabling users to query datasets, request for on-demand dataset generation and execute ELT pipelines using natural language intents. Therefore 6G-DALI will streamline the process of data collection, preparation and sharing, and position its 6G Data Space and DataOps solution as a strong foundation for effective and scalable AI/ML model training and validation in 6G networks and systems.

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